

EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING
INFORMATION SYSTEM ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE
ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS, COOPERATIVES
AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA

IMPACTS ATTENDUS DE L'IMPLANTATION D'UN SYSTEME
D'INFORMATION MARKETING SUR LA PROMOTION DE
L'ENTREPRENEURIAT FEMININ : CAS DES ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES ET PME DE LA REGION DE SOUSS MASSA DARAA

CHAKOR ABDELLATIF

Professeur de l'Enseignement Supérieur à l'Université Mohammed V
de Rabat, Maroc

abdellatif.chakor@um5.ac.ma

LALI KHALID

Doctorant à l'Université Mohammed V de Rabat, Maroc

khalid.lali@um5s.net.ma

Date de soumission: 22/08/2019

Date d'acceptation: 01/12/2019

DOI :

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

ABSTRACT

The aim of this article is to raise awareness of future entrepreneurs who are female of the imperative to design a marketing information system considered today as an effective tool who is serving for better planning and realization of their marketing strategies. Our problem therefore consists in identifying the expected impacts of the implementation of this system on the promotion of female entrepreneurship. The case of associations, cooperatives and SMEs from the Souss Massa Daraa area. In this setting, we specify that our research gait is hypothetico-deductive in nature and the data collection method was based on a questionnaire that we have established. The results of our analysis have enabled us to deduce that despite the persistence of several financial constraints, women entrepreneurs are still motivated by the idea of acquiring these contraptions to benefit from their operational functionalities, thanks to software such as groupware and workflow. The only constraint which we had to face in this work was the delay taken by some targeted people before answering us because they were suspicious with regard to some questions which are included in our questionnaire. Finally, we can say that on the basis of the results obtained, we are motivated by the idea of presenting in the future an econometric model in which we will explain the sustainability of a female entrepreneurial project by the determinants of efficiency and the reliability of these strategic and operational supports.

KEYWORDS: Female entrepreneurship, marketing information system, Groupware, Workflows.

RESUME

L'objectif de cet article est de sensibiliser les futures porteuses de projet entrepreneurial à l'impératif de concevoir un système d'information marketing considéré aujourd'hui comme un outil efficace au service d'une meilleure planification et concrétisation de leurs stratégies marketing. Notre problématique consiste donc à identifier les impacts attendus de l'implantation de ce système sur la promotion de l'entrepreneuriat féminin. Cas des associations, coopératives et PME issues de la région de Souss Massa Daraa. Dans ce cadre, nous précisons que notre démarche de recherche est de nature hypothético – déductive et la méthode de collecte des données s'est basée sur un questionnaire que nous avons établi. Les résultats de notre analyse nous ont permis ainsi de déduire que malgré la persistance de plusieurs contraintes financières, les femmes entrepreneures sont toujours motivées à l'idée d'acquérir ces engins pour bénéficier de leurs fonctionnalités opérationnelles et ceci grâce à des logiciels tels que les groupware et le workflow. La seule contrainte à laquelle nous avons dû faire face dans ce travail a été le retard pris par quelques personnes visées avant de nous répondre car elles ont été méfiantes vis-à-vis de certaines questions prévues dans notre questionnaire. Enfin et en se basant sur les résultats obtenus, nous pensons présenter ultérieurement un modèle économétrique où on explique la pérennité d'un projet entrepreneurial féminin par les déterminants de l'efficacité et la fiabilité de ces supports stratégiques et opérationnels.

MOT CLES : Entrepreneuriat féminin, système d'information marketing, collectif, coordination et enchaînement automatisées des tâches.

INTRODUCTION

Today, companies that succeed and resist adapting to competition are those that design their business strategies on customer orientation based on the promotion of creativity and innovation. In concrete terms, it involves mobilizing all human, technical and financial skills to find credible answers to customers' expectations by offering them quality products and services. As a result, marketing science is committed to winning this satisfaction challenge. In other words, its role is to identify the needs of target markets and to deliver the desired customer satisfaction in a cost-effective and more efficient way than the competition. In this context and given the blatant death rate of SMEs in Morocco, it is important to note the great success demonstrated by the woman entrepreneur who managed to lead her company to success by developing new products and services from unmet needs and future needs of existing markets or needs arising from the release of new techniques or technologies. It must be said that this success is due to several factors that have favored such a feat. These can be classified into three categories namely: the financial incentive strategy (motivation), the human and technical management of human capital (in-house development of skills through training or outsourcing) and finally the mastery of technological tools for strategic and operational decision-making (for example optimization tools). Indeed, female entrepreneurs who want to succeed in creating added value must combine several variables such as the profile of the female entrepreneur, her level of education, experience, technical and managerial skills and the spirit of entrepreneurship and creativity, etc. On the other hand, no one can deny that currently the survival capacity of Moroccan women-run enterprises depends on their ability to predict external changes and to adapt. Indeed, the promotion of women's entrepreneurship requires that the woman leader be proactive and seize all information in order to act faster than her competitors and thus to be able to benefit from market opportunities. Thus, the entrepreneurial woman is called better than ever to think of weaving new business relationships, creating new organizational configurations, mobilizing and motivating her team, retaining her clients, identifying the needs of her prospects and monitoring her competitors, because its current or future rivals are all adopting new management techniques, methods or tools. In this respect we believe that Marketing Information Systems (SIMK) are supposed to play a key role in the success and continuity of women's entrepreneurship because they provide the required information the company needs at the right time for efficient operation and effective management of its commercial function, thus constituting a source of competitive advantage. The added value of these information

EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS, COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA

systems will be enormous as they will be able to support managerial decision-making and increase the efficiency of the organization and consequently increase sales and profits.

The woman leader must finally use her marketing information system to identify her strengths and develop them if she wants to differentiate as long as possible but also to list its weaknesses in order to be aware of various drastic threats that could contribute to the disappearance of his company and thus to prepare in advance the appropriate hedging instruments to guard against these threats.

The purpose of this article is to answer the following question: How to promote female entrepreneurship using a marketing information system? Cases of associations, cooperatives and SMES in the Souss Massa Daraa area.

Two hypotheses emanate from this problem, namely:

H1: Succeeding in promoting women's entrepreneurship through a marketing information system is conditioned by the preparation of a favorable organizational and strategic climate.

H2: Computerization of processes is the key to success for women's entrepreneurship.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE GENESIS OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Interest in the concept of female entrepreneurship appeared in 1970 thanks to the research work of several authors, notably Brush; 1992; Carrier, Julien and Menville, 2006, and gained momentum in the early 1990s through feminist theories (Hurley 1999, Fisher et al., 1993, Greer and Green 2003). In this sense, it is interesting to emphasize the importance of three theories on which the research adopted by Greer and Green (2003), which is dedicated to women entrepreneurs, namely Feminism Liberalism (FL), Marxist Feminism (FM) and Radical feminism (FR).

- Liberal Feminism has studied in depth the appropriate measures that are necessary to achieve equality between the two genders at the legal and institutional levels. According to this trend, the persistence of such barriers limits access to and integration of women into the labor market through its big doors, like their male counterparts, the possibility of taking up managerial positions of responsibility, the feasibility of building partnerships and alliances to seize business opportunities and access funding (Brush 1992, Greer and Green 2003).

According to the authors defending this theory, notably Ahl (2006), men and women are essentially similar and equal. According to this design, the differences between the two sexes come from racial and discriminatory behaviors (Marlow and Patton, 2005, Carter and Williams,

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

2003), and it is therefore the role of liberal feminism to eliminate all forms of inequality against women entrepreneurs. For example, if there are differences registered in the level of turnovers, profitability, productivity and returns on investment between firms run by men and those run by women, authors like Francine Richer and Louise St-Cyr (2007: 45) emphasize the need to design specific and strengthened training programs, as well as highlighting the role of mobilizing the experience of certain skills key within the company.

- Marxist Feminism (FM) aimed to eliminate racial and sexist injustice in addition to economic overexploitation to achieve economic equality. The authors of these theories aimed instead to promote the contribution of women's domestic work as actors creating added value in the economy.

- Radical Feminism: According to the proponents of these theories, the male sex is better privileged to succeed the challenge of entrepreneurship and that is the reason why we prefer to give men more benefits and support them to make them beings higher than women because of her responsibilities as a spouse and also because she deals with the upbringing of children.. On the other hand, this finding is justified by the fact that women entrepreneurs succeed less and generate lower results than their male counterparts, especially in terms of job creation, turnover and profit (Robert D Hisrich and Brush, 1983, Cuba, R, Decenzo, D. and Anish, A. 1983, Longstreth, Stafford and Mauldin, 1983, Brush, 1992). Indeed the motive that stimulates the desire to undertake in women is not necessarily the search for financial gains but rather, autonomy and flexibility. In this context, Buttner and Moore (1997) argue that the main motivations of women who have opted for an entrepreneurial career are the desire of the challenge, the determination and the willingness in addition to the need to find a balance between personal life and professionals responsibilities (Watson and Robinson, 2003). Work-family balance therefore appears to be a major challenge for women entrepreneurs. The goal is to balance the demands of family and work life with improved living standards through the creation of income-generating activities (Kimberly A Eddleston and Gary N. Powel, 2012, 2013). So, we can say that given a constantly changing environment and in order to continue to exist and stay alive as long as possible, the woman leader does not need to be the best manager, but she must perceive the opportunity before the others, be endowed with a spirit of imagination, creativity, know to put forward its own capacities and especially to be sufficiently mature to manage correctly the risk of failure.

2. THE MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM AS A STRATEGIC PILOTAGE TOOL FOR THE PROFIT OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Convinced of the importance of having real weapons to plan appropriate actions through their data warehouses, companies, with the emergence of relationship marketing and personalization of customer relations, are starting to realize the usefulness of constituting customer databases and try to exploit them. We are all aware of the added value that the implantation of marketing information systems can bring as a new indispensable IT tool enabling to forge real personalized relationships with each client and in view of the evolution of marketing which has gone from a vision marked by the predominance of materiality and continuous transactions towards a new vision characterized by immateriality, today's companies are preoccupied with adopting innovative and operational strategies that will enable them to establish, maintain and enhance business relationships with their clients, taken one-by-one in order to retain them over the long term. Of all the above and given the importance of these new automated tools that are the marketing information systems, we agree to opt for the definition of KOTLER (P) and DUBOIS (B) according to which: *"A System marketing information combines people, equipment and procedures to gather, sort, analyze and disseminate useful, necessary and relevant market, competition and environmental information to marketers to help them to make their decisions"*. The advantage of these marketing information systems as decision support systems is enormous since it becomes possible to be able to analyze a process in time at different stages and this by using techniques such as Datamining. In addition, these systems are equipped with software and applications of great importance including groupware and workflows.

2.1. DATA MINING (DATA EXTRACTION)

Data mining is a way of analyzing and interpreting a large volume of data from different sources in order to identify trends, gather similar elements into statistical categories, and formulate hypotheses. It brings together a set of data analysis tools to significantly increase the amount of information a company has about its customers to assist in decision-making.

From the information collected, the company will be able to obtain objective answers on which to base its vision. The centralization of customer data must facilitate the management of all the activity of the company. Thus, it will be necessary to differentiate the customers according to their needs and their contribution to the result and to dialogue with them so as to reduce the costs of the commercial relation and to increase the efficiency.

2.2. THE GROUPWARE

The groupware is an application that allows dispersed teams to perform together and interactively a common task. It also allows organizing remote meetings or working sessions. These forms of organization are particularly adapted to horizontal teams, that is to say within which there is no strong hierarchical relationship but rather an implication in a common project.

2.3. WORKFLOW

Workflows are planning software less oriented towards collaboration but rather to the coordination of chained tasks. Unlike groupware, workflow prescribes tasks, controls execution, and manages the use of time. They make it possible to control an upstream downstream process and optimize the management of information and time. They thus undoubtedly present aspects of taylorization of intellectual work.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Given the lack of empirical studies focused in highlighting the added value of the implementation of a marketing information system on the success of an entrepreneurial project designed and led by women in associations, cooperatives and SMEs, the nature of our research is essentially descriptive, exploratory and analytical. Thus, it seemed interesting to draw up a questionnaire relating to a description of the professional context preceding the arrival of its decision-making systems as well as to the reasons justifying the importance of the use of these computer tools in a future female entrepreneurial project undertaken in the region of Souss Massa Darâa. To reach do this, the questionnaire was therefore mainly focused on the following points:

- What credible motives legitimize the need to invest in the implementation of a marketing information system as part of a women's entrepreneurial project?
- Can these computerized systems be considered as tools for self-adjustment of strategies adopted to better match the objectives and results expected by women leaders?
- What kind of resources will the woman leader need to be convinced of the success and efficient continuity of these computerized processes?

The questionnaire that has been established is composed of several indicators to test the validity of pre-established hypotheses and which has been distributed to the various decision makers as well as management stakeholders in associations, cooperatives and some SMEs from the region of Souss Massa Darâa.

- The answers to the survey questions led to the creation of a quantifiable database.

EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS, COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA

- The answers were entered and processed by the SPSS software.

Data processing was done using Factor Correspondence Analysis (FCA) since it is a qualitative variable followed by Dynamic Cloud Analysis.

3.1. QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to be able to answer the problematic of this article and test the validity of our two hypotheses initially established, we based ourselves on two analyzes (intra bloc and inter bloc) completed by an automatic classification:

3.1.1. INTRA BLOC ANALYSIS

The purpose of this analysis is to group together the respondents and the variables corresponding to the different indicators made and to identify, from this group, certain deductions. A descriptive analysis of the data collected from the survey leads to an idea of the characteristics of the people surveyed; For example, it is necessary to check whether the respondents are young or old, single, divorced or widowed. Stakeholders in the various organizations (associations, cooperatives and SMEs) were also identified by function, professional status, legal status of the organization, number of children in charge, tasks performed, etc. We then described the current professional climate as well as the main expectations expressed by the respondents with regard to the marketing information system, without forgetting to highlight the difficulties encountered in filling the gaps in human and financial resources. .

3.1.2. INTER BLOCK ANALYSIS

In order to test the validity of each of our two hypotheses initially stated at the beginning of this article we proceeded to the simultaneous and combined analysis of the indicators constituted for each of the two variables taken separately. The goal is to group people and variables and identify some similarities.

3.1.2.1. DEFINITION OF VARIABLES AND INDICATORS

Before analyzing the data extracted from this survey, we identified each variable by indicators. Thus the variable "**RPFE = Requirements for Promoting Female Entrepreneurship**" was represented by the following indicators:

- The Exchange of relevant information between colleagues «ERIC ».
- The number of years of experience of each person « NYEP ».

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

- Management style « MAGS ».
- The requirement of completion deadlines for tasks assigned to each employee « RCDT».
- The spirit of communication and listening «SCL».
- Disposition of human, material and financial resources « DHMFR».
- Computer skills and knowledge « DCSK ».
- Marketing positioning based on customer expectations and needs « MPCE».
- Continuing training for staff « CTFS ».

The variable "**EBMIS = Expected Benefits of Implementing a Marketing Information System on female entrepreneurship**" can be represented by the following indicators:

- Flexibility « FXP ».
- Adoption of new managerial practices « ANMP »
- Collaborative and team work « CTW »
- The Productivity and profitability « PRT »
- Customer loyalty « CUSL »
- The attraction of new customers « ACUS»
- Computerized management of processes within the organization « CMPO»
- The Automatic tracking of tasks performed by each person « ATTP ».
- The restructuring of the organization « RESO »
- The autonomy « AUT »
- The disposition of ratios and indicators to succeed in a future marketing strategy « DRSM »
- The estimate of sales to be realized « ESLR ».
- The valuation of products and / or services « VAPS »

And lastly the variable "**EACP = Efficiency of an Appropriate Computerization Process**", was determined from the following indicators:

- The automatic formalization of rules and procedures «AFRP»
- The instant satisfaction of the user needs «ISUN »
- The respect of predetermined deadlines

- The robustness in the processing of internal and external data of the organization «RPIED »
- Design a clear and understandable marketing and sales strategy «DCMSS »
- Streamlining and optimization budgets and time of the organization « SOBT»
- Tracking the history of sales made to different customers «THSC »
- Economies of scale. « ECSC »

3.1.3. THE NON-HIERARCHICAL AUTOMATIC CLASSIFICATION

The objective of this technique, based on the dynamic cloud method, which sets the number of classes of the partition from the outset (based on certain characteristics collected from the respondents), is to constitute homogeneous groups of individuals. In other words, we try to group people who are alike (have the same visions) and separate those who are remote and this by making a reduction fixed in advance of the number of individuals.

4. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS AND IMPLICATIONS OF RESULTS

After having collected, coded and entered the data from our investigation we passed to the step of analysis which will allow us to invalidate or confirm our two hypotheses identified at the beginning of this article.

4.1. THE ANALYSIS OF QUANTITATIVE RESULTS

To describe in a synthetic way the observed data to better analyze them, we proceeded initially to a descriptive analysis (intra bloc analysis) followed by a combined and simultaneous analysis of two big blocks of indicators that we composed for judge the relevance of our two hypotheses resulting from our problematic announced at the beginning of this article.

4.1.1. THE INTRA BLOC ANALYSIS

This analysis allowed us to come out with the following results:

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

Figure 1: Distribution of artisanal cooperatives according to the gender approach

**Source: Survey conducted among associations, cooperatives and SMEs in the Souss
Massa Daraâ area in 2018-2019.**

According to the survey conducted on artisanal cooperatives in the Souss Massa Daraâ area, we note that:

- 31.94% of the cooperatives are in the city of Errachidia, 12.50% are located in Erfoud, 6.94% in Rissani, 9.72% in Goulmima, 11.11% in Tinjdat, 12.50% in Mdaghra, 9.72% in El Khang, 4.17% in Aoufous and finally 1.39% are located in Boudneb.

On the other hand, it can be deduced from the respondents' answers that:

- Of the total number of cooperatives in Errachidia (23 cooperatives) 95.65% are specialized in production (ie 22 cooperatives) and only one in service (ie 4.35%).
- It is also interesting to note that of the totality of the managers of the cooperatives 47.83% are women and 52.17% are men.
- A horizontal and vertical analysis of this distribution of cooperatives stratified by sector of activity and sex also leads us to conclude that almost the majority of cooperatives are specialized in production except the cooperatives located in Errachidia, Goulmima and Tinjdat (where we find specialized cooperatives in service).
- In addition, one can also deduce that the female sex exists massively in the cooperatives of Boudneb, Aoufous, Mdaghra, Goulmima and Tinjdat, (on the other hand we can see that the representativity of the two sexes is relatively the same to Errachidia and Erfoud), and that the only predominantly male city with a focus on cooperative work is the city of Rissani (80% men versus 20% women).

Gender and age analysis of the members of the organizations encountered

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

Diagram N°1: Analysis of age and sex structure

Source: Survey conducted among associations, cooperatives and SMEs in the Souss Massa Daraâ area in 2018-2019.

According to the respondents' answers, we have 57.72% of women and 42.28% of men.

The analysis of age groups of both sexes also allows us to come out with the following conclusions:

- Of all the respondents (149 people), 8.05% are men and the age is between 20 and 24 years, against 8.72% who are female and have the same age range .
- Of the surveyed population aged between 25 and 29 years, 5.37% are men and 16.78% are women.
- 16.11% of respondents are female and are between the ages of 30 and 34, compared to 5.37% who are in the same age group but are male.
- Persons aged between 35 and 49 years old are distributed as follows; 15.44% are men and 14.77% are female.
- Of all respondents aged between 50 and 54, we have 6.71% of men and 1.34% of women.
- Finally, 1.34% of respondents are aged 55 and over and are all men.

Current civil status of the respondent

From this diagram, we can read that:

30.20% of the members of the organizations met are still single; 46.31% are married; 18.12% are divorcee(ed) and finally 5.37% are widow(er).

Number of children in charge by the person surveyed

An analysis of the number of children in charge per person working in the different organizations visited gives the following results:

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

20.13% have one child in charge; 10.07% reported having two children; 12.08% reported having three children, 14.09% had four children; finally, 2.01% have five children in charge. However, it is important to note that 34.23% of respondents were suspicious of this point and therefore decided not to reveal the number of children they care.

High Education Level of the Interrogated Person

The analysis of the high level of education of each questioned led us to leave with the following results:

16.78% have university certificates; 15.44% hold a Diploma of General University Studies (DGUS); 21.48% have a Bachelor's degree; 3.4% have a Master; 12.75% of graduates (ie holders of a Baccalaureate); 6.71% hold a Diploma of Professional University Studies (DPUS); 8.72% have a College Diploma and finally 10.1% have not completed high school.

Legal status of the organization

We note that 31.54% of the organizations surveyed are composed of associations; 44.97% of cooperatives, 12.08% of individual companies; 6.04% of participation company (SP); 4.03% of limited liability companies (SARL) and finally 1.34% are the company in collective name (SNC).

Sector of activity of the organization

By analyzing the organizations according to their sectors of activity, we could observe that: 40.94% are specialized in handicrafts, especially textiles; 23.49% are interested in agriculture, especially livestock and pisciculture; 4.03% are specialized in the fishing industry; 13.42% give a lot of importance to foodstuffs; 0.67% are specialized in the exploitation of medicinal and aromatic plants; 6.04% are in dairy products; 3.36% are in printing and stationery; 2.7% in trading and finally 5.35% find their reasons to be in the services provided to orphans and disabled people.

In addition, a reading of the hierarchical positions occupied by the respondents within the different organizations leads us to affirm that:

- Respondents from associations and cooperatives break down as follows:

12.08% are presidents, 10.07% are vice presidents; 22.15% are advisor, 9.40% treasurers and 4% are General Secretary.

We also note that among the members within the associations and cooperatives surveyed, we find 5.4% retired.

- For people working in the companies visited, we have 9.4% employees, 4.7% associates; 16.78% owners and 2% managers.

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

Finally, we have 4.02% composed of the members intervening in ordinary and extraordinary assemblies organized by these organizations.

Number of years of existence of organizations

Regarding this point, we have been able to deduce that 12.08% of organizations are newly created; 35.57% operate two years ago; 32.89% exist six years ago; 12.08% have been in existence for ten years and 7.38% of organizations have been in existence for more than ten years.

Main reasons for investing in entrepreneurship

57.72% of the carriers of innovative ideas say that the decision to invest in entrepreneurship was by necessity and obligation in order to be able to provide for the needs of life that has become expensive.

On the other hand, 42.28% say that in fact the real reason they moved to the business field was to seize opportunities so it was much more a choice to make on the part of the latter.

Characteristics of the working conditions before the implementation of a marketing information system

From the answers gathered we can analyze the following:

- 43.62% of respondents say that they have been living for some time in stressful work situations; 11.41% believe that the internal climate of work within organizations is marked by conflicts of interest and 44.97% think that the internal work environment is characterized by a favorable climate, so consider that all the ingredients for the success and development are present.

- With respect to the external competitive environment to which the organization is exposed: 51.68% think it is dynamic and in permanent motion, while 48.32% believe that it is a stable environment that can be easily controlled.

Other results identified from the responses analyzed include the following:

- 69.13% of respondents believe that there is no sharing of experience between colleagues working in these organizations, against 30.87% according to which we manage to share skills and knowledge for the good of organizations.

- 61.07% admit that the working climate does not allow cooperation between colleagues within same services and also between different departments, against 38.93% who see that there is always mutual support and cooperation between the members involved in his organizations, which are always supported by the superiors. - 67.79% of

EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS, COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA

respondents point out that in their organizations there is asymmetry of information, however 32.21% think that the desired information is always available and sent to each member at any time.

-61.07% of respondents are convinced that there is an urgency to improve the management styles adopted by decision-makers, while for 38.93% of interrogated, managerial practices are in harmony with the expected and realized results

- On the other hand and according to 67.11% of respondents, organizations are not able to handle unforeseen changes that are induced by the environment, against 32.89% of respondents who think that organizations are flexible and arrive adapt in most of the times and design appropriate actions in order to deal with each situation (eg a threat and / or opportunity) caused by the external environment.

- According to 66.44% of respondents, the accumulation of several years of professional experience in several organizations was enough to stimulate their desire and willingness to enter the business world, against only 33.56% who think that success in the field of women's entrepreneurship does not necessarily depend on professional experience. In fact, these respondents put a lot of emphasis on the desire to take risks as a catalyst for investing in women's entrepreneurship.

Main sources of funding organizations

According to the survey conducted:

- 18.2% of respondents indicate that the main source of funding for activities comes from personal savings.

- 5.3% of organizations fund their activities from inheritance funds; 15.20% of bank credits; 26.4% of government program grants; 30.8% of family support and friends, and finally 4.4% of donations from charitable organizations.

4.1.2. INTER BLOCK ANALYSIS

4.1.2.1. SIMULTANEOUS ANALYSIS OF "EBMIS" AND "RPFE"

The application of the factorial analysis of the correspondence and classification into two classes of dynamic clouds on the two variables "EBMIS" and "RPFE" allowed us to group the stakeholders of the organizations surveyed into two groups such as it is presented in the figure below, which shows the dispersion of the surveyed members according to the indicators of the two variables.

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

Figure N°2: Simultaneous analysis of "EBMIS" and "RPFE"

Source: Survey conducted among associations, cooperatives and SMEs in the Souss Massa Daraâ area in 2018-2019.

The two factors F1 and F2 which result from the reduction of the indicators representing the two variables "EBMIS" and "RPFE" account for 68% of the total variability (40% for F1 and 28% for F2). From the figure, it can be said that there are two groups of people.

The first group to the right of the figure above is made up of the members of organizations who have been optimistic about the future of women's entrepreneurship following the subsequent implementation of decision support systems, namely marketing information system. These individuals expect that the new applications integrated into the systems to be implemented can generate several advantages notably: the improvement of the flexibility, the autonomy in the decision making, the increase of the productivity as well as the volumes of sales, customer loyalty, the restructuring of the internal organizations, the automatic and instantaneous monitoring of the tasks assigned to employees and finally a better steering in terms of management thanks to the ratios and indicators that will be available and provided by the new IT tools that will be installed. It is also important to emphasize that these same individuals are convinced that the continuity of existence of women entrepreneurs in a fierce market through the use of such marketing information systems is possible because current organizations have all the necessary conditions to such a success, for example, in this context: the availability of a qualified and experienced workforce, with a particular sense of listening and communication, who can anticipate the needs and expectations of customers by offering them products and quality services, appropriate logistics, good management style, decent financial resources and finally Continuing and specific training programs.

The second group located at the top left is made up of respondents who are not convinced of the feasibility of later success of a project to implement a marketing information system because, according to them, and so that these new systems of marketing information can win

EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS, COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA

the challenge of female entrepreneurship, it was necessary to prepare in advance some favorable working conditions (which are still not yet filled) especially: transparency, the distribution of tasks between employees, the human resources, material and financial, the management style adopted by managers which must have a medium and long-term vision, and finally the importance of skills with specific characteristics that can create added value for managers women especially that these last operate in a continuously changing market.

4.1.2.2. SIMULTANEOUS ANALYSIS OF "EACP" AND "RPFE"

The application of the factorial analysis of the correspondence and the classification into two classes of dynamic clouds on the two variables "EACP" and "RPFE" gave us the figure below.

Figure N°3: Simultaneous analysis of "EACP" and "RPFE"

**Source: Survey conducted among associations, cooperatives and SMEs in the Souss
Massa Daraâ area in 2018-2019.**

The two factors resulting from the reduction of the "EACP" and "RPFE" indicators explain 20% of the variability for F1 and 12% for F2. The AFC and the dynamic class classification into two classes allowed us to identify the following two groups:

The first group to the southwest is composed of people who say that all the ingredients for an effective computerization process exist: a good collection of the needs of each staff, executives having had successive passages in several companies and having knowledge and skills in IT and management before being recruited, a culture of group work and communication between all components of organizations, flexible organizations where there is no asymmetry of information, computer equipment in line with the software solutions envisaged by the computerization project, a good strategic planning with a dashboard prescribing the tasks entrusted to employees with deadlines for completion and which is supervised by high-level managers since they have accumulated several years of professional experience. This group of people thinks that this computerization project will be beneficial for women's entrepreneurship

EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS, COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA

but emphasizes the importance of factors such as retention of employees through financial incentives (motivation) but also recruitments and training without forgetting the need to introduce security and data protection policies that should always be revised.

The second group located in the North and South East consists of people who do not believe that the process of computerization required by the subsequent implementation of a marketing information system will succeed in continuing to be operational because - according to them - the current organizations suffer from several specific financial and human deficiencies. Indeed, many of the organizations visited continue to face difficulties, especially with regard to the granting of credits, and according to these, the arguments put forward by the credit institutions to justify the rejections made are not convincing.

In addition, this group considers that currently the selection criteria adopted by the organizations to choose the beneficiaries to the trainings are not credible and it's not by chance that we usually end up choosing the wrong people which could harm the success of such a project. Finally, these people think that the technical installations are not at the level of such a project and that the leaders must first of all seek to maintain a durable and fruitful relation with the customers but also to cultivate on the staff, the desire of learn, passion for victory, customer obsession and group work that are very important to prepare them for a big project such as marketing information system.

4.2. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

According to the survey carried out, we have established several questions whose answers were either affirmative or negative (that is to say that for each question we propose answers with "yes" or "no"). This point therefore aims to explain the reasons that would motivate organizations that are mostly women-led to invest in the implementation of marketing information systems. We therefore note the following:

- 59.1% of respondents think that new automation generated by marketing information systems will allow staff to work independently, while 40.9% do not agree with this result.
- The possibility of having ratios and indicators was raised by 61.7% against 38.3% who do not share the same opinion.
- The restructuring of the internal organization (77.2% think it is feasible against 22.8% who do not believe that it is possible with this implementation.

The visibility of all the tasks performed by each employee within the organization was the opinion of 56.4%, against 43.6% are not convinced of the possibility of rigorous and automatic monitoring tasks assigned to each staff.

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

- 67.1% of those interviewed consider that the marketing information system will allow the historical follow-up of the marketing strategies adopted, compared to 32.9% who think that this will not be achieved even with the implementation of this marketing information system.
- 69.1% of respondents admit that the marketing information system will contribute to the improvement of flexibility, against 30.9% who do not believe that these tools are operational to promote flexibility within organizations.
- 80.5% of respondents, especially the hierarchical superiors of the organizations surveyed, are highly motivated to implement these marketing information systems, believing that they will have a significant positive impact on productivity, marketing positioning, turnover and profitability in organizations. In addition, only 19.5% state that productivity, turnover and profitability will be maintained or reduced due to the absence of certain skills which, if they existed, should make it possible to properly control the use of these marketing information systems to put in place; However, there is a real shortage of human resources with specific skills that will be key to a successful marketing information system.
- A marketing information system will provide a collaborative and team work environment was the expectations of 54.4% of those interviewed who hope that it will be realized as soon as possible. However, 45.6% believe that installing these marketing information systems will not directly generate this spirit of collective work that will also require other factors. According to them, for example, we cannot do without real physical contact to perform certain specific tasks.
- Finally, 60.4% of respondents expect that marketing information systems that will be programmed in the future will offer a great opportunity to adopt new managerial practices which will have consequences for example on customer loyalty and the attraction of new customers thanks to the design of innovative products and / or services of better quality. However, for 39.6% of respondents, adopting a good management style to succeed in the field of entrepreneurship is conditioned not only by a climate of computerized exchange but especially by other elements whose importance should never be omitted to know, the listening and communication skills, the professional experience, the training, the conflict management, the marketing strategies based on simple actions, clear, understandable and accepted by all staff, etc. It must be said that these people think that these marketing information systems are important. Thus, to guarantee their success, these systems must be combined with the elements mentioned above and take into account the lack of quantity and quality of human and technical resources for which the organizations must devote the necessary importance.

4.2.1. THE MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

Thanks to the results of our study conducted as part of this modest work, we were able to understand and deduce that for the majority of women entrepreneurs surveyed, marketing information systems are perceived as efficient and operational tools that will support their adopted managerial practices. Furthermore, and according to these female managers, these mechanisms - where sophisticated software is integrated - aim above all to allow them to continue to exist in the competitive market since they will be at the basis of the design and activation of appropriate marketing strategies and therefore be able to respond to the needs of their customers in a faster and more profitable manner. In fact, the analysis of the data collected has revealed that the arrival of these marketing information systems will allow the bearers' women of innovative ideas to identify who is doing what? when? how often? and how? In other words, these information systems will be at the service of a good rational governance of the human and financial resources which are made available to these organizations surveyed. In addition, they will induce better collaboration, team spirit, communication and information exchange between the different employees. Finally, these strategic and operational supports will be at the base of the stimulation of a good flexibility and productivity among each staff who will no longer be obliged to return at each moment to their line manager to make a decision since with these new contraptions he has the possibility of doing so but within the limit of its scope of intervention that has already been set for it beforehand.

CONCLUSION

Given the lack of previous work having treated a specific problematic similar to that which is the subject of our article and like all research in management sciences, our study was therefore interested in filling this void by highlighting the importance of the setting up a marketing information system in the promotion and the continuity of existence of an entrepreneurial project managed by the female sex. Indeed, this article thus proposes scientific results which could be used as a reference model in order to improve the capacity of intervention, anticipation and adaptation of the women entrepreneurs who are supposed to act permanently in a competitive environment in continuous mutation. Our objective has therefore been to sensitize the bearers's women of innovative projects and who fit into the framework of an association, cooperative or creation of a small and medium-sized businesses to the necessity for implantation and appropriation an marketing information system which will allow them to leave a traceability on the history of past decisions as well as the needs previously expressed by each client and which will therefore help them to establish an appropriate marketing strategy. In this context and among the conclusions that we were able to identify from our survey conducted of women leaders belonging to these associations, cooperatives and small and medium-sized enterprises installed in the Souss Massa Darâa area is that the majority of these respondents is optimistic about the implementation of these mechanisms. In other words, these women entrepreneurs are convinced that these tools will allow them: to follow the tasks entrusted to each staff, greater flexibility and autonomy, a culture of collaborative work and a stimulation of productivity, which will then have a positive impact on the turnover that will be achieved by these organizations. However, it is also important to note that the survey carried out revealed obstacles which continue to block women entrepreneurs from appropriating these systemic mechanisms - which serve to better manage and activate major marketing decisions - in particular the acquisition cost as well as the maintenance costs of these automations (in case of failure of these) and which remain still high, the insufficient means of financing which must be devoted to the planning of specific training programs without forgetting also the lack of technical and managerial skills required by these new ways of working. Within this framework, we have also noticed that these organizations targeted by this study still cannot cover all their financial difficulties and needs even by deciding to call on the financial institutions for granting credits, since the latter always prefer to present many arguments and justifications for not give a favorable response to their funding requests. On another side, we would like to point out that

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

the main constraint that we had to face in order to reach our objective initially put forward at the beginning of this article is that the questionnaire established as a means of data collection was made up a few specific questions which aroused great reluctance and mistrust on the part of the respondents who were afraid of being judged afterwards thus calling into question their experiences and especially their managerial skills and this is what explains why they took a long time before answering to our questionnaire. Finally and considering the limits of this study as well as the constraints that continue to prevent women with innovative entrepreneurship ideas from being able to set up these marketing information systems, we think it would be really very interesting to focus our future research work on establishing an econometric model explaining the key variables on which the efficiency, robustness and reliability of these strategic and operational supports are based and which can explain the success and sustainability of an entrepreneurial project and this by also adopting a method of collecting mixed data. It is clear that if we act this, we aim rather to detail the main current obstacles still hampering the appropriation of these tools by women entrepreneurs as well as the solutions to be adopted today by these in order to be able to take maximum advantage of operational functionalities which are offered by these automatisms. In other words, the variable to be explained is the success and sustainability of a female entrepreneurial project and the explanatory variables are the determinants of an effective, reliable and robust marketing information system.

**EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM
ON THE PROMOTION OF FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CASES OF ASSOCIATIONS,
COOPERATIVES AND SMEs IN THE SOUSS MASSA DARAA AREA**

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL REFERENCES

FERRAY M. (2010), "Do women influence business performance?", The journal -Work-Gender and Societies, vol.1, no 23, pp. 181-190.

JENNINGS, J.E, CANDIDA G. Brush, C.G. (2013), "Research on Women Entrepreneurs: Challenges to (and from) the Broader Entrepreneurship Literature?", The Academy of Management Annals Journals, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 661–713.

BENJAMIN BADIA et al. (2013), "The brakes and obstacles to female entrepreneurship. Qualitative study of business creators in the agglomeration of Nancy", The Social Research Journal, vol.4, no 208, pp. 7-57.

CORNET, A. & CONSTANTINIDIS, C. (2004), "Women's entrepreneurship: A multiple reality and differentiated expectations", French Management Review, vol.4, no 151, pp. 191-204.

SALVADOR, A.B. & IKEDA, A.A (2014) "Big Data Usage in the Marketing Information System", Journal of Data Analysis and Information Processing, vol. 2, no 3, pp. 77-85.

CHAUDHARY, P., HYDE, M. & RODGER, J.A. (2017) "Exploring the Benefits of an Agile Information System", Intelligent Information Management-Scientific Research Publishing, vol.9, no 5, pp.133-155.

H. METHUKU AND H. RAMADAN (2013) "A Study on Developing the Role of Human Resource Information Systems for Good Leadership" American Journal of Industrial and Business Management- Scientific Research Publishing (SCIRP), vol. 3, n°5, pp. 497-506.

ANDREKI, P.H.A. & YAZDANIFARD, R. (2014) "Is E-Marketing the Future of Marketing Field?" American Journal of Industrial and Business Management- Scientific Research Publishing (SCIRP), vol. 4, no. 7, pp. 333-336.

J. WANG, Z. LIN AND H. HUANG (2008), "A Decision Model for Information Systems Outsourcing: Using a Multicriteria Method" Journal of Service Science and Management - Scientific Research Publishing (SCIRP), vol. 1, no. 1, 2008, pp. 1-10.

S. AL-FEDAGHI, R. ALLOUGHANI AND M. SANOUSI (2012) "A New Methodology for Process Modeling of Workflows" Journal of Software Engineering and Applications - Scientific Research Publishing (SCIRP), Vol. 5, no. 8, pp. 560-567.

FLETCHER, K., BUTTERY, A. AND DEANS, K, (1988), "A structure and content of the marketing information system: a guide for management", Marketing Intelligence and Planning. Vol. 6 No. 4, pp. 27-35.